

Discovery of Lunar Vertical Holes and Caverns: In 2009, observations by the Japanese lunar probe SELENE (Kaguya) revealed vertical holes measuring several tens of meters in diameter and depth in Marius Hills, Mare Tranquillitatis, and Mare Serenitatis¹⁻³). These holes are hypothesized to be skylights formed by the collapse of the ceilings of underground caverns, such as lava tubes created by volcanic activity. The Moon's lava is basaltic, similar to that found on Earth in locations such as Hawaii Island, Mount Fuji, and Jeju Island in Korea, where lava tubes exist. This similarity suggests that similar lava tubes may also exist on the Moon^{e.g.4}). Subsequent oblique observations by the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) confirmed that horizontal voids extend from the bottom of these vertical holes⁵).

Lunar lava tubes are considered promising sites for future space exploration bases because their interiors offer protection from meteorite impacts, radiation, and extreme temperature fluctuations^{3,4}). Additionally, numerous similar vertical holes have been discovered on Mars^{6,7}), making the exploration of underground caverns on extraterrestrial bodies a crucial aspect of future space development.

UZUME Project and Its Objectives: Currently, the "UZUME (Unprecedented Zipangu Underworld of the Moon/Mars Exploration)" working group has been established⁸). This initiative aims to explore lunar and Martian vertical holes and underground caverns from both scientific and lunar base construction perspectives. The project is led by approximately 50 researchers from the Institute of Space and Astronautical Science (ISAS) at the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) and various domestic universities (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The Japanese academia plans to build a lunar base for humans in an underground cavern on the Moon. from Japan Society of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Space Vision 2050 ©JAXA

Four Bases Planned for the Mid-2030s: The UZUME group aims to begin constructing four bases in lunar underground caverns by the mid-2030s. The team is currently developing preliminary plans for technological demonstrations and scientific exploration.

Activity Base: The Moon presents a unique environment, especially with its gravity being only 1/6 that of Earth. This reduced gravity opens up opportunities for developing novel sports and activities. Unlike the lunar surface, underground caverns provide a safer and more stable environment, making them ideal for recreational use. Additionally, these caverns possess unique geological and aesthetic features, making them valuable for tourism.

Resource Development Base: One of the most promising lunar resources is helium-3, which is being considered for use as a nuclear fusion fuel as well as a low-temperature coolant. While nuclear fusion was once regarded as a distant dream, recent technological advancements have brought it closer to practical application. Helium-3 is believed to be concentrated near the lunar equator and in regions with high titanium content⁹), including areas around Marius Hills and the vertical hole in Mare Tranquillitatis (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Distribution of titanium on the near side of the Moon (from LRO-QMAP). The warmer colors indicate areas with more titanium. There is a lot of titanium around the holes on the Moon (the star on the left indicates the hole in the Marius Hills, and the star on the right indicates the hole in the Mare Tranquillitatis).

Storage Base: As sample return missions from Mars and asteroids become more common, a facility may be required to temporarily store and analyze samples containing potential life-origin materials before they are brought back to Earth. Lunar under-

ground caverns could serve as curation centers for such materials.

Additionally, projects such as the long-term storage of Earth's biological DNA¹⁰ and the establishment of a data center for artificial intelligence processing are under consideration. The stable temperatures within equatorial lunar caverns (approximately -20°C to 0°C)^{3,4,11} make them an ideal environment for such facilities.

Scientific Research Base: The Apollo program conducted five landings in the Moon's mare regions, providing significant insights into lunar geology. However, recent remote sensing and landing exploration missions have revealed that many aspects of lunar volcanic activity and underground structures remain unknown.

For example, the thin lava layers observed in vertical hole walls⁵ and the formation mechanisms of underground caverns are still subjects of ongoing study. These caverns may also provide crucial information about the Moon's past magnetic field and its evolutionary history. Establishing a research base within these caverns would enable direct sample collection and in-situ analysis, significantly advancing our understanding of the Moon's origin and evolution.

4. Summary

Lunar vertical holes and underground caverns are of great interest from a scientific point of view. In addition, they are also important targets for future exploration and utilization. Under the UZUME program, nearly 50 Japanese scientists and engineers are engaged in defining how to explore and utilize these underground spaces by the mid-2030s (Fig.3). The program follows a strategy of exploration, demonstration, and eventual construction of lunar bases.

Moving forward, the program aims to strengthen collaboration with private companies and international space agencies, marking a new step in lunar and furthermore Martian exploration.

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Fig.3. The timeline of the UZUME program (not have been approved). A goal is to establish a human-inhabited operating base in an underground cavern on the Moon by the mid-2030s, and then backcast from there to plan technology demonstration and scientific exploration missions.